

Period of Induction of Chemical Reactions. Part II. Action of Hypophosphorous Acid on Sodium Iodate.

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The liberation of iodine by the reduction of iodates by hypophosphorous acid has been mentioned by Vitali (*Boll. Chim. farm.*, 1899, 38, 201) but we have observed that appreciable time elapses before the liberated iodine makes its appearance; the conditions and causes governing this induction period, *viz.*, the influence of dilution, temperature, light etc., form the subject-matter of the present communication. The belated appearance of iodine as judged by the period of induction is, in all probability, due to successive reactions in the oxidation of the iodate to the ultimate product namely iodine.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Solutions of sodium iodate and hypophosphorous acid were prepared and their concentrations determined iodometrically (*cf.* Sutton, Volumetric Analysis). The stock solutions were diluted according to requirement. Boiling tubes containing 10 c. c. of each solution were kept before a white back-ground in a thermostat, regulated to the required temperature and when the solutions had acquired the temperature of the bath, the iodate solution was poured quickly into the hypophosphorous acid solution, stirred once and the time before the appearance of iodine noted by means of a stop-watch. A starch solution was employed to indicate the appearance of iodine but it was abandoned, because the blue colour took considerable time to develop.

In the following tables C_h represents the concentration of hypophosphorous acid and C_i that of the iodate in g. moles per litre and T , the induction period in seconds.

TABLE I.

	Temp. = 28° 4.	$K = T \times C_i \times 10^2.$									$C_h = .249.$
C_i0162	.0324	.0435	.0647	.0807	.0969	.1133	.1792	.1290	.145
T	...	360	180	195	91	73	60.4	52	33	48	39.8
K	...	58.32	58.32	58.72	58.87	58.91	58.52	58.91	58.41	58.65	58.00

The induction period varies inversely as the concentration of the iodate, that of the acid remaining constant.

TABLE II.

	Temp. = 28°·2.	$K = T \times C_A \times 10.$					$C_i = \cdot 0162.$			
C_A	... ·00996	·0133	·0149	·0179	·0199	·0218	·0239	·0249	·0278	
T	... 199	142·4	135	110	100	90	84	78	70	
K	... 19·92	18·94	19·11	19·71	19·90	19·62	19·08	19·52	19·46	

The induction period varies inversely as the concentration of the acid, that of the iodate remaining constant.

Thus the induction period varies inversely as the concentration of the acid as also that of the iodate. This conclusion was verified by further experiments, in which concentrations of both were varied; this will be evident from Fig. 1, in which concentration of the mixed solution is plotted against the time.

FIG. 1.

TABLE III.

Influence of Temperature.

	"A"									
	$C_A = \cdot 0249.$					$C_i = \cdot 0323.$				
Temp.	... 30°	35°	40°	45°	50°	55°	60°	65°	70°	
T	... 160	147	128	107	90	72	50	27	8	
Temp. coeff.	...	4·2	3·8	4·2	3·4	3·6	4·4	4·6	4·0	

“B”

	$C_h = \cdot 0253.$					$C_i = \cdot 0498.$				
Temp.	... 30°	35°	40°	45°	50°	55°	60°	65°	70°	
<i>T</i>	... 539	478	420	360	298	230	168	110	58	
Temp. coeff.	...	12	11.6	12	12.4	13.3	12.4	11.6	12.4	

FIG. 2.

Thus the period of induction diminishes regularly with increasing temperature.

Influence of Alcohols.—Measured volumes of different alcohols were introduced into the boiling tubes containing the acid, kept in the thermostat. The iodate solution at the same temperature was quickly poured into the mixture, which was then stirred.

TABLE IV.

	$C_h = \cdot 0248.$				$C_i = \cdot 0506.$								
Ethyl alcohol (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	4	6	8	10					
<i>T</i> (Temp. = 27°)	...	89	178	220	300	398	525	630					
Methyl alcohol (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	4	6	8	10					
<i>T</i> (Temp. = 27°·4)	...	89	74	62	55	49	40	28					
iso-propyl alcohol (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	4	6	8	10					
<i>T</i> (Temp. = 27°·4)	...	89	100	312	390	471	585	720					
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol (c.c.)	...	0	·5	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<i>T</i> (Temp. = 28°)	...	89	No appearance of colour of iodine even after 1800 sec.										

Ethyl alcohol lengthens the induction period considerably, whilst methyl alcohol shortens it. This contradictory behaviour of the alcohols is not understood on the basis of polarity and associative power of the two solvents and probably viscosity enters into the phenomenon. Of the two isomeric propyl alcohols, *n*-propyl alcohol lengthens the induction period so enormously that no iodine appears even after the lapse of half an hour and this remarkable divergence may be utilised as a qualitative method of differentiating the two isomeric alcohols.

TABLE V.

Influence of Butyl Alcohols.

$C_A = \cdot 0433.$			$C_i = \cdot 0249.$			Temp. = 28°·6.		
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol (c.c.)	...	0	1		iso-Butyl alcohol	...	0	1
<i>T</i>	...	178	312		<i>T</i>	...	178	31

The above experiments were performed in order to examine if the structure of the isomeric alcohols contribute to the peculiar results obtained with the two isomeric propyl alcohols. The limited solubility of the butyl alcohols stood in the way of extension of observation with these. The results show that the effect exerted by these alcohols is of a complicated nature.

TABLE VI.

Effect of Glycerol.

$C_A = \cdot 0249.$		$C_i = \cdot 506.$						Temp. = 26°·8.	
Glycerol (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	4	6	8	10	
<i>T</i>	...	95	140	190	290	400	490	598	

Glycerol thus increases the period of induction, in conformity with our previous observations (Neogi and Neogi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, p. 30; Neogi and Mukherji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1229, 6, 529).

TABLE VII.

Effect of Salts.

$C_k = \cdot 0249.$			$C_i = \cdot 0506.$			Temp. = 28°·4.		
Salt.	Conc. (N).	T.	Salt.	Conc. (N).	T.	Salt.	Conc. (N).	T.
Potassium chloride	... 1·5583	152	Potassium citrate	... ·3298	194			
Sodium chloride	... „	151	Sodium citrate	... „	191			
Potassium nitrate	... 1·3431	168	Potassium sulphate	... 1·3946	162			
Sodium nitrate	... „	159	Sodium sulphate	... „	160			
Potassium tartrate	... ·3109	180	Without salt	... —	87			
Sodium tartrate	... „	175						

The period of induction is thus influenced specifically by each kind of salt and the influence appears to be due to anions and independent of cations.

The effect of sugars was next investigated. It was found that cane sugar practically exerts no influence, while grape sugar, fruit sugar and mannose slightly increase the period of induction.

TABLE VIII.

Effect of Geometrical and Optical Isomers.

$C_k = \cdot 249.$		$C_i = \cdot 0339.$		Temp. = 28°·4	
Isomer.		Conc. (N).		T.	
—		—		189	
Maleic acid	...	·06531		207	
Fumaric acid	...	„		224	
d-Tartaric acid	...	·7787		255	
l-Tartaric acid	...	„		285	

The induction period is influenced to a greater extent by fumaric than by maleic acid at the same concentration. *l*-Tartaric acid has a greater effect than *d*-tartaric acid.

Effect of Solvents.

The effect of solvents of iodine, which are themselves insoluble in water, was next investigated. Carbon tetrachloride, benzene, chloroform, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene, *p*-xylene and carbon disulphide were tried. These were found to diminish the induction period considerably and the comparative influences appear to follow the order of solubility of iodine in these solvents, as would be seen from the following table.

TABLE IX.

$C_k = \cdot 0323.$		$C_i = \cdot 0238.$						
				Temp. = 27°·7.				
Carbon tetrachloride (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	4	6	8	10
<i>T</i>	...	212	155	92	44	40	32	21
				Temp. = 27°·5.				
Carbon disulphide (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	4	6	8	10
<i>T</i>	...	213	177	152	110	80	60	50
				Temp. = 28°.				
Benzene (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	4	6	8	10
<i>T</i>	...	210	126	105	74	52	30	10
				Temp. = 28°.				
Chloroform (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	4	6	8	10
<i>T</i>	...	210	146	97	74	60	48	36

Influence of Finely Divided Metals.—The effect of finely divided metals was next investigated. It was found that these reduce the period of induction greatly; the different metals studied stand in the order, $\text{Mg} \geq \text{Al} \geq \text{Zn} \geq \text{Ni}$.

TABLE XII.

Influence of Thiosulphate.

$C_1 = .0323.$	$C_1 = .0288.$				Temp. = 29°.			
Thiosulphate conc. (N)	...	0	.0125	.025	.05	.1	.5	1
T	...	215	57	38	25	15	6	

FIG. 3.

It may be mentioned that a similar instance of thiosulphate enhancing the speed of chemical reaction has been observed by Judson and Walker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 73, 410) in the reaction between HBr and HBrO_3 . The readiness of the appearance of iodine was enhanced by the addition of a little ammonium chloride to the reaction mixture. For instance, 2 drops of $N\text{-Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ gave an induction period of two seconds but previous addition of about 1 g. of NH_4Cl caused the induction period to disappear. Probably sodium iodate, in presence of ammonium chloride, oxidises sodium thiosulphate to tetrathionate, liberating a small quantity of iodine (Jørgensen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 19, 18). A portion of the added thiosulphate is converted into tetrathionate and iodide and the iodic acid

(iodate in presence of hypophosphorous acids) present in excess gives rise to iodine (Reigler, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1896, 35, 308). The small quantity of iodine thus liberated is taken by thiosulphate and more and more iodine is produced. This explains the apparent anomaly.

TABLE XIII.

Influence of Thiosalts.

$C_h = \cdot 0249.$ $C_i = \cdot 0645.$ Temp. = 29°·2.

1 C.c. of the reagent was used at each experiment.

Reagent.	Conc. (N).	T.
Ammonium thiocyanate ...	·05	6
Sodium tetrathionate ...	·05	3
Without addition ...	—	90

TABLE XIV.

$C_h = \cdot 0288.$ $C_i = \cdot 0323.$ Temp. = 29°·2.

Conc. of KI = ·1854 N.

Vol. of KI soln. (c.c.)	...	0	0·5	1	2	3	4	5
T	...	212	109	81	58	32	14	nil.

Thus potassium iodide, added previously to the reaction mixture, reduces the induction period considerably, the reduction being proportional to the concentration of the iodide. An observation, somewhat similar to this, has been made by Purakayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 726), who found that in the case of photochemical induction between bromine and tartaric acid, potassium bromide added to the system previously considerably reduced the induction period.

Influence of Colloidal Sulphur Sol.—The sulphur sol was prepared by Raffo's method, by the interaction of sulphuric acid and sodium thiosulphate followed by dialysation.

TABLE XV

$C_A = .0249.$		$C_i = .0147.$				$\text{Temp.} = 29^\circ.$		
Sulphur sol (drops)	...	0	2	4	6	8	10	15
T	...	396	22	15	10	6	3	0

FIG. 4.

Sulphur sol has thus a marked effect on the induction period. This cannot be readily explained but it should be remembered that sulphur is more exceptional in its adsorbability and chemical reactivity amongst colloidal sols.

TABLE XVI.

Influence of Platinum Black and Animal Charcoal.

$C_A = .0249.$		$C_i = .0645.$		$\text{Temp.} = 28^\circ.4.$
Substance.		Wt.		T
—		—		93
Platinum black1 g.		7
Animal charcoal1		12

Animal charcoal reduces the induction period to a marked extent, to which apparently no single cause may be adduced. Platinum black probably exerts such a decreasing influence by the liberation of hydrogen in the nascent state by reacting with NaH_2PO_2 formed in the course of the reaction, which acts much in the same way as in the case of the action of the finely divided metals on the induction period.

Critical Concentration and Period of Induction.— The process followed consisted in altering the concentration of one of the reactants, the concentration of the other being fixed and observing the induction period, until a concentration was obtained, at which there was no period of induction and iodine appeared immediately.

TABLE XVII.

$C_h = \cdot 0172.$					Temp. = 29°.	
$C_i \dots$	1826	·3652	·5478	·7304	·9130	greater than ·9130
$T \dots$	6	3·4	2·0	1·4	less than 1 sec.	0

Influence of Light.— Solutions of sodium iodate and hypophosphorous acid were prepared in a dark room, provided with a ruby lamp. Two drops of starch solution (.5 g. of starch in 50 c.c. water) were added to indicate the colour. Since the results were meant for comparison only, the period of induction between starch and iodine did not vitiate the observed effects.

TABLE XVIII.

$C_h = \cdot 0249.$	$C_i = \cdot 0339.$	Temp. = 280·2.
	T	
In Light ...	190	
In Dark ...	189	

Thus the induction period is not influenced by light.

Summary.

(1) The reaction between sodium iodate and hypophosphorous acid has a considerable period of induction, in so far as iodine appears after the lapse of considerable interval from the initial time of mixing the solutions and the period of induction is not influenced by light.

(2) The period of induction is dependent on the dilution of the reactants, the higher the dilution, the greater is the period of induction. Thus the following relations have been found to hold good:

$$K = T \times C_h, \quad \text{when } C_h \text{ i.e. the acid conc. is const.}$$

$$K = T \times C_i, \quad \text{,, } C_i \text{ i.e. the iodate conc. is const.}$$

$$K = T \times C_h \times C_i, \quad \text{,, both } C_h \text{ and } C_i \text{ are varied,}$$

T , being the period of induction and K , a specific const, for each case.

(3) Increase in temperature causes a decrease in the period of induction.

(4) Of the alcohols, ethyl alcohol causes an increase in the period of induction, while methyl alcohol produces the reverse effect. *n*-Propyl alcohol totally inhibits the reaction, while *iso*-propyl alcohol increases the induction period. The *n*- and *isobutyl* alcohols behave similarly.

(5) The period of induction increases in presence of glycerol, chlorides, sulphates, nitrates, citrates, tartrates, glucose, laevulose and mannose.

(6) The period of induction diminishes in presence of solvents of iodine like carbon tetrachloride, benzene, carbon disulphide, hexane, toluenes and chloroform, the diminution being greatest in the case of benzene and least in the case of carbon disulphide.

(7) Optical isomers like *d*-tartaric acid and *l*-tartaric acid and geometrical isomers like maleic and fumaric acids have considerable influence on the induction period, *l*-tartaric acid, and fumaric acid causing greater increase in the induction period than *d*-tartaric acid and maleic acid respectively.

(8) The presence of dilute mineral acids causes a decrease in the period of induction.

(9) Sodium thiosulphate, even in minute quantities, causes a remarkable diminution in the period of induction and in certain concentrations causes complete disappearance of the induction period. Ammonium thiocyanate and sodium tetrathionate act in a similar manner.

(10) Potassium iodide causes considerable diminution in the induction period and under certain circumstances causes it to disappear altogether.

(11) Colloidal sulphur sol markedly causes diminution of the period of induction.

(12) Oxidising agents have generally little influence on the induction period.

(13) Reducing agents and finely divided metals cause a decrease in the period of induction.

(14) Platinum black and animal charcoal exert marked influence in diminishing the period of induction.

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